

Preparation of Glucose Syrup from Waxy Corn by Enzymatic Process

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Abstract

Starch was prepared from waxy corn. Enzymatic hydrolysis of prepared corn starch was carried out via two steps, viz., liquefaction by enzyme α -amylase and saccharification by enzyme glucoamylase. The optimal conditions for those hydrolysis reactions were determined. The Dextrose Equivalent (D.E) values of hydrolysates were also determined by Lane and Eynon's Method. The liquefaction reaction was found to be optimum at D.E value 12.8, pH 6, starch substrate concentration 25% (wt. %), dosage of α -amylase 1.5 mL, reaction temperature 95°C and heating time of 15 minutes. Similarly, the saccharification reaction was optimum at D.E value 80.34, pH 4, enzyme dosage 2.5 mL, reaction temperature 60°C and heating time of 3 hours. In addition, the establishment of application of prepared glucose syrup in osmotic dehydration process was studied. For this purpose, osmotic dehydration of apple, sweet potato and banana (Rakhine banana) were conducted. Comparison on osmo-sun dried products and traditional sun-dried products were also made.

Key words: liquefaction, saccharification, D.E value, osmotic dehydration

Introduction

Most green plants produce starch as a means of energy storage. Starch is a polymer of glucose units. Starch hydrolysis is the cleaving of the starch polymer to short chain fragments such as dextrans and maltose or to glucose monomer.

Enzymatic starch hydrolysis is a form of biochemical modification. Depending on the extent of enzyme hydrolysis, a range of chain lengths corresponding to glucose (dextrose), maltose, oligosaccharides and polysaccharides can be produced. The exact composition can be determined by measuring the Dextrose Equivalent (D.E) value, where a D.E of "100" corresponds to pure dextrose and a D.E of "0" to native starch. The liquefied product has D.E value in the range 8-15 and the saccharified product has D.E value above 15.

Enzymatic starch hydrolysis is carried out via two steps, viz., liquefaction of gelatinized starch by enzyme α -amylase and saccharification of liquefied starch by enzyme glucoamylase.

Gelatinization is a process in which an aqueous suspension of starch is heated, the hydrogen bonds weaken, water is absorbed, and the starch granules swell. Liquefaction is a process in which the breakdown of starch polymer reduces the viscosity of gelatinized starch. Saccharification is the final stage of depolymerization to form mono-, di-, and tri-saccharides.

Glucose syrup is used as sweetener in confectionery, jam, ice-cream, desert, biscuit and brewing industries. Glucose syrup is also used as anti-crystallizing agent in ice-cream or jellies. Additionally, glucose syrup is used as osmotic substance in osmotic dehydration of fruits, vegetables and meats. Osmotic dehydration is a method for the partial dehydration of water-rich food by immersing them in osmotic solution. Osmotic dehydration is to allow the removal of water from the water-rich foods without undergoing the phase change, nutritional, sensorial and functional properties of foods giving a potential for energy saving in comparison with conventional drying. Products obtained by hot-air drying method have low porosity and significant color and textural changes occurred due to this process. Also, sun-dried products have high microbial load.

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Materials and Methods

Materials

The raw corn was obtained from Hopone Township, Southern Shan State, Myanmar. Enzymes were kindly provided by M.Y. Associated Co., Ltd. located at Dagon Centre, Sanchaung Township, Yangon.

Reagents

Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, sodium potassium tartarate and sodium hydroxide.

Methods

Separation of Starch from Corn

The raw waxy corn was carefully inspected. Cob, dust, weed seeds, chaff and foreign materials were removed. About 1.5 kg of cleaned corn was steeped with 2 L of water at 50°C for about 24 hours. After steeping, the steeped water was drained off and softened corn was ground in 2 L of water in a blender for 3 minutes. The ground slurry was sieved through an 80-mesh screen, and the residue was washed with 2 L of water until all of starch granules were washed off. The filtrate was then sieved through a 200-mesh screen. The starch-gluten slurry that was passed through 200-mesh screen was allowed to stand for one and half hours. The water and gluten layer were removed by decantation. Then, the starch layer was resuspended followed by sedimentation and decantation. The residual protein was removed by scrapping off all non-white material and the wet starch was dried in an oven at 60° C for 4 hours. The dried starch was ground in a grinder and sieved through 200-mesh screen and stored.

The prepared starch was analysed for moisture content and ash content. The results are shown in Table 1.

Gelatinization of Starch

About 25 g of starch was mixed with 100 mL of distilled water and heated to 70°C with continuous stirring. Heating and stirring were carried out until the starch was completely gelatinized. Then, the gelatinized starch was cooled to room temperature.

Liquefaction

The cooled gelatinized starch was adjusted to pH 6-6.5 by using 0.5 M phosphate buffer solution. About 1.5 mL of heat stable α -amylase was added into it. Then, the mixture was heated to 90-100°C for 15 minutes with continuous stirring. The liquefied starch, i.e., maltodextrin was obtained. The liquefied starch was cooled to room temperature and determined for Dextrose Equivalent value by Lane and Eynon's method. Determination of optimal conditions for liquefaction– substrate concentration, pH of medium, dosage of enzyme, heating temperature and reaction time-were carried out. The results are shown in Table 2 - 6.

Saccharification

The cooled liquefied starch was adjusted to pH 4.0-4.6 by using 0.5 M phosphate buffer solution. About 1 mL of glucoamylase enzyme was added into it. Then, the mixture was heated to 60°C for one hour with continuous stirring. Finally the glucose syrup was obtained. The glucose syrup obtained was analyzed by Lane and Eynon's method for determination of Dextrose Equivalent value. In addition, determination of optimal conditions for saccharification– dosage of enzyme, reaction temperature and heating time were carried out. The results are shown in Tables 7 - 9.

Determination of Dextrose Equivalent Value

About 25 mL of mixed Fehling's solution was placed in a 150 mL conical flask. The sample solution, i.e. starch hydrolysates was added into a 50 mL burette. The flasks and contents were heated to boil. After the solution was allowed to boil for 2 minutes, 2 drops of methylene blue indicator was added into the flasks. As boiling continued, the sample solution was added into the flask in small portions to furnish complete the reaction until the blue color disappeared within 2 minutes. The end point was recorded as the appearance of the bright red color of copper oxide in the solution.

The D.E value of starch hydrolysate, as dextrose, can be calculated on the basis of the solid matter as following.

$$\text{D.E} = \frac{\text{reducing sugar content as dextrose}}{\text{total solid}} \times 100$$

Results and Discussion

For the separation of starch from corn, the wet milling method was used and the prepared starch was analysed for physical and chemical characteristics. The respective data are shown in Table 1. From these results, it was found that, the values of ash content, moisture content and yield percent are comparable to those of literature values. So, it was concluded that the prepared corn starch is suitable to use for further processing.

Table 1. Properties of Prepared Corn Starch

No.	Corn Grain		Corn Starch			
	dry wt. (g)	moisture (%)	ash (%)	moisture (%)	dry wt. (g)	yield (g%)
1	385.0	5.0	0.3	15.0	189.0	49.0
2	300.0	5.0	0.3	17.0	148.0	19.3
3	400.0	5.0	2.6	17.0	220.0	55.0
4	250.0	7.0	0.2	16.0	143.0	57.1
5	400.0	6.0	0.2	16.0	232.0	58.0
Literature value *	-	-	0.15	13.5	-	61.7

For liquefaction process, the results obtained for determination of optimal concentration of substrate are shown in Table 2. From these results, it is evident that the maximum D.E value was obtained at substrate concentration of 25 g. It was found that, the D.E value decreased at higher substrate concentration. The most favourable pH value to obtain maximum D.E value was found to be of pH 6 as shown in Table 3. At higher pH value, it was found that the activity of enzyme is slower and D.E value is also lower. For the effect of enzyme dosage (Table 4), the optimal enzyme dosage for predetermined optimal substrate concentration was found to be of 1.5 mL. From the results shown in Table 5, the optimal reaction temperature was found to be at 95°C. The reaction temperature that was higher than 100°C were not examined in this work due to the intensive boiling and formation of foam at atmospheric pressure. According to Table 6, it was found that the maximum D.E was obtained at 15 minutes reaction time.

Table 2. Effect of Substrate Concentration on D.E Values of Liquefaction Products

No	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp (°C)	Enzyme Dosage (mL)	Time (min)	Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
1.	15.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	253.5	3.61	7.0
2.	20.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	366.3	3.87	9.5
3.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	501.9	4.09	12.3
4.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	523.6	4.02	13.0
5.	30.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	416.4	4.16	10.0
6.	30.0	100	6.3	95	1.5	15	446.8	4.38	10.2
7.	35.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	327.4	3.92	8.4

Table 3. Effect of pH on D.E Values of Liquefaction Products

No	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp (°C)	Enzyme Dosage (mL)	Time (min)	Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
1.	25.0	100	4.0	95	1.5	15	243.6	6.96	3.5
2.	25.0	100	5.0	95	1.5	15	377.6	6.09	6.2
3.	25.0	100	6.0	95	1.5	15	501.9	3.92	12.8
4.	25.0	100	7.0	95	1.5	15	431.1	3.99	10.8
5.	25.0	100	8.0	95	1.5	15	431.1	4.18	10.3
6.	25.0	100	9.0	95	1.5	15	253.5	3.52	7.2

Table 4. Effect of Dosage of Alpha-Amylase Enzyme on D.E Values of Liquefaction Products

No	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp (°C)	Enzyme Dosage (mL)	Time (min)	Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
1.	25.0	100	6.1	95	0.5	12	243.6	5.41	4.5
2.	25.0	100	6.1	95	0.75	15	377.6	5.72	6.6
3.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.0	15	327.4	3.83	8.55
4.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.25	15	431.1	3.81	11.3
5.	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	446.8	3.53	12.64
6.	25.0	100	6.1	95	2.0	15	431.5	3.67	11.75

Table 5. Effect of Temperature on D.E Values of Liquefaction Products

No	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp (°C)	Enzyme Dosage (mL)	Time (min)	Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
1.	25.0	100	6.2	30	1.5	15	377.6	5.72	6.6
2.	25.0	100	6.1	45	1.5	15	253.5	3.40	7.45
3.	25.0	100	6.1	60	1.5	15	446.3	4.41	10.12
4.	25.0	100	6.1	75	1.5	15	431.1	3.96	10.87
5.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	523.6	3.99	13.12

Table 6. Effect of Heating Time on D.E Values of Liquefaction Products

No	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Enzyme Dosage (mL)	Time (min)	Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
1.	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	10	366.3	3.83	9.56
2.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	501.9	4.09	12.28
3.	25.0	100	6.3	95	1.5	30	501.9	4.34	11.66
4.	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	45	501.9	4.30	11.57
5.	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	60	501.9	4.40	11.40

The optimal conditions for liquefaction step, as describe in above, were chosen to carry out the next step, i.e. saccharification. For saccharification of liquefied corn starch, the results obtained from studying the influence of enzyme dosage are presented in Table 7. From these results, it is evident that the D.E value 80.34 was the maximum at enzyme dosage of 2.5mL. For the effect of reaction temperature (Table 8), the optimal reaction temperature for saccharification was found to be of 60°C. It was found that the D.E value decreased at higher temperature. According to Table 9, it was found that the maximum D.E value was obtained at 3 hours heating time.

For studying the application of prepared glucose syrup, the osmotic dehydration treatment effects were studied on apple, sweet potato and Rakhine banana. The appearance of traditional sun-dried products and osmo-sun dried products are comparatively illustrated in Figures 1 - 9. These figures best described that osmo-sun dried products were found to be more satisfactory and attractive to consumers.

Table 7. Effect of Dosage of Enzyme Glucoamylase on D.E Values of Saccharification Products

No.	Liquefaction						Saccharification				Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Dosage of α -amylase (mL)	Time (min)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Dosage of gluco-amylase (mL)	Time (h)			
1	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	1.00	1	668	1.11	65.58
2	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.2	60	1.25	1	707	1.04	68.16
3	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	1.50	1	707	1.01	70.48
4	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.2	60	1.75	1	707	1.00	75.00
5	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	2.00	1	751	0.96	78.05
6	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.3	60	2.50	1	801	0.99	80.34
7	25.0	100	6.3	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	3.00	1	801	0.996	80.37

Table 8. Effect of Reaction Temperature on D.E Values of Saccharification Products

No.	Liquefaction						Saccharification				Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Dosage of α -amylase (mL)	Time (min)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Dosage of gluco amylase (mL)	Time (h)			
1	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.1	50	2.5	1	707	1.01	69.82
2	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	2.5	1	801	0.99	80.34
3	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	4.2	70	2.5	1	707	1.04	68.24
4	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	4.1	80	2.5	1	276	4.66	59.26
5	25.0	100	6.3	95	1.5	15	4.3	90-100	2.5	1	259	5.14	50.53

Table 9. Effect of Heating Time on D.E Values of Saccharification Products

No.	Liquefaction						Saccharification				Dextrose /100 mL (mg)	Total solid /100 mL (g)	D.E Value
	Corn Starch (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Dosage of α -amylase (mL)	Time (min)	pH	Temp. (°C)	Dosage of gluco amylase (mL)	Time (h)			
1.	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	2.5	1	801	0.99	80.34
2.	25.0	100	6.1	95	1.5	15	4.2	60	2.5	2	801	0.90	88.90
3.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	2.5	3	801	0.89	90.52
4.	25.0	100	6.2	95	1.5	15	4.1	60	2.5	4	801	0.88	90.54

Conclusion

Starch was separated from waxy corn in this work. When the properties of prepared corn starch were compared with literature, it was found that the prepared corn starch was of acceptable quality. After the liquefaction process, the product obtained was maltodextrin. Comparison on the D.E value of prepared maltodextrin with that of literature indicated that its D.E value was in good agreement. Similarly comparing the D.E value of saccharified products with literature value, it was clearly seen that the prepared glucose syrup has a remarkable increase in D.E value as described in literature. Osmotic dehydration treatment able to retain the flavor and the color of fresh fruit by minimizing thermal changes and also prevented enzymatic browning. Sun dried products have numerous defects such as high microbial load, undesirable appearance, color and brightness and high shrinkage. This research revealed some of the ways and means to bring about improvement of dried foods with lower water activity, higher shelf-life and potential energy saving.

Figure 1. Apple (Raw)

Figure 2. Apple slices (sun dried)

Figure 3. Apple slices (osmo-sun dried)

Figure 4. Sweet potato (Raw)

Figure 5. Sweet potato slices (sun dried)

Figure 6. Sweet potato slices (osmo-sun dried)

Figure 7. Rakhine banana (Raw)

Figure 8. Rakhine banana (sun dried)

Figure 9. Rakhine banana (osmo-sun dried)

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Online Materials

1. <http://www.cassava.big.org/postharvest/g.syrup.0.1.htm>
2. <http://www.uctm-edu/journal/2007-3/16-kdusheva-93-96-pdf>
3. <http://pdf.org/pdf/effect-of-osmotic-predehydration-on-drying-characteristics-of-banana-fruit>.
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